

Milestone: M1.3 First stakeholders event**Lead Participant:** ELIXIR**Author:** Serena Scollen, Nikki Coutts**Due:** 31/01/2026**Date Of Completion:** 27/02/2026

Means of Verification

Report written on the B1MGplus and GDI outputs providing value to other EU data space projects today and in the future:
<https://zenodo.org/records/18848305>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Project participants & others

Serena Scollen, ELIXIR Hub
Juan Arenas, ELIXIR Hub
Nikki Coutts, ELIXIR Hub
Ellie Younger, ELIXIR Hub
Melissa Konopko, ELIXIR Hub
External presenters:
Jeroen van Rooij (Genome of Europe, ERASMUS MC)
Morris Swertz (ERDERA, UMCG)
Lifang Liu (CANDLE, Health-RI)
Peter Gordebeke (EUCAIM, EIBIR)

Next action steps

